

Kinetics and Mechanism of Halogenation Reactions Involving Some Aromatic Primary Amines (Part II)

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Kinetics of the reactions of aniline and a few substituted anilines with CAT in aqueous acetic acid-HClO₄ mixtures and in aqueous acetic acid and sodium acetate buffers is reported. The reactions are first order in CAT and first order in the aromatic base. The reactions are faster in aqueous acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer than in aqueous acetic acid-HClO₄ mixtures for all amines except for paranitro aniline. This confirms our earlier finding that it is the free base which reacts for all amines except for *p*-nitro aniline where the protonated form is the reactive species. A competition between the protonation process and the effect of dielectric constant of the system on the reaction rate is observed at an above 0.025 M HClO₄. Kendall's treatment has been applied to compute the acid independent rate constants which have been used for comparison of structure and reactivity.

In our previous communication¹ we have shown that chloramine-T (CAT) chlorinates aniline, *p*-chloro aniline, *p*-toluidine and *p*-nitro aniline at measurable rates and evidences were presented for direct halogen transfer. The present communication is concerned with kinetics of chlorination of aniline, *o*-chloro-aniline, *o*-toluidine, *m*-chloro aniline and *m*-toluidine by chloramine-T in aqueous acetic acid.

Materials and Methods :

Chloramine-T of M & B make of AR grade was used without further purification. *o*-chloro aniline, *o*-toluidine, *m*-chloro aniline and *m*-toluidine were of BDH AR grade and were distilled before use. The disappearance of CAT was estimated by standard iodometric method. The rate constants have been computed by the usual tangential method.

Stoichiometry :

Stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by taking the substrate in excess as well as by taking the CAT in excess; the former to judge the reaction steps during kinetic runs and the latter to judge the overall reaction products. The equivalence of CAT per mole of substrate in the two cases has been found to be 1 and 2 respectively. Thus the reaction under conditions of kinetic run can be represented as :

On the other hand, the overall reaction with excess of CAT proceeds further to halogenate the monochloro product and hence the reaction is :

the yields of isolated monochloroanilines under the experimental conditions were greater than 80%.

Results and Discussion :

In the concentration range employed in the study the reactions are second order : first order in the substrate and first order in the halogenating agent. The earlier idea that aromatic chlorination is zero order in the substrate² does not seem to hold good, as the first order rate constant increases with increasing concentration of the substrate confirming the first order nature with respect to the substrate (Table 1). Variation of CAT in the concentration

TABLE 1
10% AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID, 0.0125 M HClO₄,
CAT=0.00045 M, TEMP 35°

Substrate	Concentration of substrate	k ₁	k ₂ 1. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Aniline	0.004512	0.0007334	0.1625(0.08125)
	0.005951	0.0009433	0.1585(0.07925)
	0.007161	0.001151	0.1607(0.08035)
<i>o</i> -cl. anilino	0.002391	0.0004411	0.1840
	0.005684	0.001106	0.1945
	0.007723	0.001431	0.1852
<i>m</i> -toluidine	0.002333	0.0004217	0.1807
	0.005461	0.001009	0.1849
	0.007747	0.001502	0.1938

range studied yields a constancy in the first order rate constant indicating the dependence on CAT as unity (Table 2).

TABLE 2
ANILINE=0.005156 M, 10% HAC, 0.0125 M HClO₄,
TEMP 35°.

CAT	k ₁ sec ⁻¹
0.0002111	0.0008026
0.0004500	0.0008172
0.0007188	0.0007723

Effect of acidity :

There is inverse dependence on acidity as compared to direct dependence in the case of *p*-nitroaniline. The differential dependence on acidity in the case of compounds under present study and *p*-nitroaniline is an important observation and is a pointer to the nature of the substrate species taking part in the reaction. It appears that the reactive species in the case of *o*-chloroaniline, *o*-toluidine, *m*-chloroaniline, *m*-toluidine is the unprotonated amine whereas it is the protonated form for *p*-nitroaniline. Such reasoning has been done earlier by Bell.³ (Table 3).

TABLE 3

10% AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID, CAT=0.00045M, TEMP 35°.

Substrate	k_2 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			
	H ⁺ =0.00606M	H ⁺ =0.0125M	H ⁺ =0.025M	H ⁺ =0.05M
<i>o</i> -cl. aniline	0.2698	0.1945	0.1694	0.1090
<i>o</i> -toluidine	0.2291	0.1610	0.1292	0.06757
<i>m</i> -cl. aniline	0.2099	0.1672	0.1212	0.08079
<i>m</i> -toluidine	0.2878	0.1819	0.1119	0.05843

Solvent effect :

Increasing acetic acid percentage decreases the rate and also increase in ethanol percentage decreases the rate, pointing to the fact that it is dipole-dipole reaction between CAT and amines. Plot of log₁₀ k_2 vs 1/D and log₁₀ k_2 vs D-1/2D+1 are linear (Table 4 & 5).

TABLE 4

 HClO₄=0.0125 M, CAT=0.00045 M, Temp. 35°.

Substrate	k_2 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			
	10% AcOH	20% AcOH	30% AcOH	50% AcOH
<i>o</i> -cl. aniline	0.1945	0.1832	0.1272	0.08455
<i>o</i> -toluidine	0.1610	0.1305	0.09954	0.04308
<i>m</i> -chloro aniline	0.1672	0.1351	0.07848	0.05340
<i>m</i> -toluidine	0.1849	0.1072	0.07065	0.0385

TABLE 5

 CAT=0.00045M, HClO₄=0.0125 M, Temp. 35°.

Substrate	k_2 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹		
	10% EtOH	20% EtOH	30% EtOH
Aniline	0.1470	0.08714	0.05453
<i>p</i> -nitro aniline	0.01976	0.01391	0.0061

Structure-Reactivity :

In our previous work with aniline, *p*-chloro aniline, *p*-bromo aniline, *p*-iodo aniline, *p*-toluidine and *p*-nitro aniline, we have shown that *p*-nitro aniline reacts slower and *p*-halogeno amines and *p*-toluidine react faster. In all the cases the products are ortho chloro isomers. In case of aniline the isomer distribution is equal, the products being both para and ortho chloro isomers. Hence to compare the reactivity of the unsubstituted derivative the rate

constant is divided by a statistical factor 2 to give the partial rate with respect to ortho isomer. In the present study the reactivities of *o*-chloro aniline and *o*-toluidine are slightly higher than *p*-chloro aniline and *p*-toluidine. *m*-chloro aniline and *m*-toluidine exhibited higher reactivity as compared to the *p*-chloro aniline and *p*-toluidine. In case of meta substituted anilines two nuclear positions are available for halogenation. Hence k'_2 (Ortho) (partial rate) is computed by dividing the observed rate by a statistical factor 2. The partial rates for aniline and meta substituted anilines when taken into consideration give a clear picture of reactivity (Table 6).

TABLE 6

 10% AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID 0.0125 M, HClO₄, CAT=0.00045 M, TEMP. 35°.

Substrate	k_2 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	Substrate	k_2 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Aniline	0.1625(0.08125)	<i>o</i> -cl.aniline	0.1945
<i>p</i> -cl. aniline	0.1432	<i>m</i> -cl.aniline	0.1672(0.0836)
<i>p</i> -bromo aniline	0.1865	<i>o</i> -toluidine	0.1610
<i>p</i> -iodo aniline	0.3479	<i>m</i> -toluidine	0.1849(0.0924)
<i>p</i> -toluidine	0.1486	<i>p</i> -nitro aniline	0.02500

Comparison of rates in pure aqueous medium and in aqueous acetic acid medium at different concentrations of perchloric acid :

It is observed that with increasing percentages of acetic acid the rate decreases. Increasing percentage of acetic acid decreases the dielectric constant of the medium. Decrease in dielectric constant decreases the rate. But increase in dielectric constant increases the rate at constant acidity till 0.0125 M. But at 0.025 M and 0.05 M acidities there is near equivalence in rate with increase in dielectric constant. This near equivalence in rate at and above 0.025 M HClO₄ is much against the dependence of rate on dielectric constant of the system for dipole-dipole reactions. This requires explanation in the two competing processes (1) Increase in rate due to increase in dielectric constant of the system ; (2) Decrease in rate due to increasing the acidity ; the second factor seems to predominate at higher acidities thus leading to an apparent decrease in rate (Table 7).

TABLE 7

SUBSTRATE ; ANILINE=0.005 M, CAT=0.00045 M, TEMP 35°.

H ⁺ M	Aqueous medium	k_2 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			
		10% AcOH	20% AcOH	30% AcOH	50% AcOH
0.00603	0.7565	0.2245	0.1508	0.1186	0.0627
0.0125	0.2519	0.1625	0.1138	0.08587	0.05643
0.025	0.03642	0.1052	0.05737	0.04315	0.01879
0.05	0.06697	0.06346	0.03196	0.02221	0.01230

Effect of change of pH :

The system was changed to aqueous acetic acid-

sodium acetate buffer from aqueous acetic acid-HClO₄ to prove that it is the unprotonated amine which participates as compared to the protonated form of the *p*-nitro aniline. Reactions have been conducted in various percentages of acetic acid and sodium acetate buffers. Reactions are faster in all the cases except *p*-nitro aniline where retardation is observed as compared to the rates of aqueous acetic acid-HClO₄ mixtures. The extent of protonation will be less in aqueous acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer as compared to protonation in aqueous acetic acid-HClO₄ medium. This confirms our finding reported by us¹ that there is inverse dependence on acid for all amines except *p*-nitroaniline for which there is direct dependence on acid. Hence all the amines reacted faster as the free amine concentration increased whereas in the case of *p*-nitroaniline the protonated form which is the reactive species decreases due to less acidic system and hence retardation in rate (Table 8).

TABLE 8

CAT=0.00045 M, Temp. 35°.

Substrate	k ₂ l.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹		
	20% AcOH 0.02 M AcONa	50% AcOH 0.02 M AcONa	90% AcOH 0.02 M AcONa
Aniline	0.3723	0.2629	0.0588
<i>p</i> -cl. aniline	0.3905	0.1975	0.0465
<i>p</i> -bromo aniline	0.4935	0.2194	0.05876
<i>p</i> -iodo aniline	0.6676	0.4566	0.07736
<i>p</i> -toluidine	0.4957	0.1892	0.0464
<i>p</i> -nitro aniline	0.009714	0.003695	0.00107

Ionic Strength Effect :

Increasing the concentration of NaClO₄ does not effect the rate appreciably indicating that ionic strength effect is negligible. Further, addition of KCl in place of NaClO₄ does not alter the rate. The salt effects observed are in consonance with the dipole-dipole reactions (Table 9).

TABLE 9

CAT=0.00045 M, 10% ACETIC ACID, 0.0125 M, HClO₄, TEMP 35°. ANILINE=0.005146 M

Salt	Concentration	k ₂ l.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
NaClO ₄	0.0025	0.1963
	0.005	0.1936
	0.0075	0.1396
KCl	0.00063	0.1453

Application of Kendall's treatment :

Structure reactivity relationship can be better understood by the application of Kendall's treatment⁴ which envisages the computation of true acidity independent rate constants. The free base will exist in equilibrium with its conjugate acid ion as shown in the equation :

Applying the Hammett acidity function h₀ the con-

centration of the free base [B] at equilibrium can be calculated from log [B]=h₀-Pka+log [BH⁺] where Pka is the dissociation constant of the conjugate acid. Because the acid is in excess, the concentration of [BH⁺] can be assumed to be constant and may be taken as equal to stoichiometric amount of the base added. The first order rate constants that are obtained at different acidities, when divided by the respective effective concentrations at equilibrium, yielded second order rate constants which are very close to each other within the limits of experimental errors and with in the limitations involved in employing the treatment. The acid independent rate constants are recorded in Table 10.

TABLE 10

10% AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID, CAT=0.00045 M, TEMP. 35°.

Substrate	k ₂ l.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			
	H ⁺ =0.006M	H ⁺ =0.0125M	H ⁺ =0.025M	H ⁺ =0.05M
<i>o</i> -cl. aniline	1.782	1.581	1.991	3.415
<i>m</i> -cl. aniline	10.28	9.126	10.55	14.7
	(5.14)*	(4.563)*	(5.27)*	(7.35)*
<i>o</i> -toluidine	301.9	261.0	302.8	391.0
<i>m</i> -toluidine	228.7	180.7	158.1	230.4
	(114.35)*	(90.35)*	(79.05)*	(110.2)*

* represents k'₂ (Partial rate)

With the acid independent rate constants the order of reactivity is :

o-toluidine > *m*-toluidine > *m*-chloroaniline > *o*-chloroaniline. It is clear that the application of the treatment is quite successful for even halogenation reactions which has been tried for the first time though it has been employed for other processes⁵.

To investigate the effect of temperature and to evaluate various thermodynamic parameters, measurements were made at 25°, 30 and 35°. The results obtained for aniline at 35° are summarised in Table 11.

TABLE 11

THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR ANILINE

Substrate	E (K cal.)	ΔH (K.cal)	log ₁₀ A	ΔS [‡] (eu)
Aniline	18.31	17.69	14.76	-4.65

Of the various species of CAT, *p*-toluene sulphochloramide (CH₃C₆H₄SO₂NHCl) produced from CAT in a fast step is considered to be the active species under the experimental conditions. The *p*-toluene sulphochloramide produced in the fast step reacts in a slow step with the free base in case of substrates studied other than *p*-nitro aniline to give the products.

$$(\text{RNH}_2)_T = \text{RNH}_2 + \text{RNH}_3^+ \text{ so } \text{RNH}_2 = (\text{RNH}_2)_T / \{1 + k_2\text{H}^+\}$$

substituting for RNH_2 which is the reactive species

$$\frac{-d(\text{CAT})}{dt} = k_1 k_3 (\text{RNH}_2)_T (\text{CAT}) \dots (1)$$

On substituting for the reactive species RNH_3^+ for

p-nitroaniline $\text{RNH}_3^+ = k_2(\text{RNH}_2)(\text{H}^+)$ accordingly the rate law for *p*-nitroaniline can be

$$\frac{-d(\text{CAT})}{dt} = k_1 k_2 k_3 (\text{RNH}_2)(\text{CAT})(\text{H}^+) \dots (2)$$

The rate laws (1) and (2) are quite in agreement with the experimental results.

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